

Prospective life cycle assessment of a bioprocess design for cultured meat production in hollow fiber bioreactors

Hanna L. Tuomisto^{a,b,c,*}, Scott J. Allan^{d,e}, Marianne J. Ellis^e

^a Future Sustainable Food Systems Research Group, Department of Agricultural Sciences, Faculty of Agriculture and Forestry, P.O. Box 27, University of Helsinki, 00014 Helsinki, Finland

^b Helsinki Institute of Sustainability Science (HELSUS), P.O. Box 4, University of Helsinki, 00014 Helsinki, Finland

^c Natural Resources Institute Finland (Luke), Latokartanonkaari 9, 00790 Helsinki, Finland

^d EPSRC Centre for Doctoral Training, Centre for Sustainable Chemical Technologies, University of Bath, Claverton Down, BA2 7AY Bath, UK

^e Department of Chemical Engineering, University of Bath, Claverton Down, BA2 7AY Bath, UK

HIGHLIGHTS

- Environmental impact of C2C12 cells grown in hollow-fiber bioreactor were estimated.
- Culture medium production had the highest contribution to the environmental impacts.
- Results were most sensitive to cell metabolism and mass increase in differentiation.
- Optimization of the culture medium composition helps to reduce the impacts.
- Use of renewable energy sources reduces the environmental impacts.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

ARTICLE INFO

Editor: Deyi Hou

Keywords:

Environment
Novel foods
Carbon footprint
Cultivated meat
Cell-based meat
Livestock

ABSTRACT

The aim of cellular agriculture is to use cell-culturing technologies to produce alternatives to agricultural products. Cultured meat is an example of a cellular agricultural product, made by using tissue engineering methods. This study aims to improve the understanding of the potential environmental impacts of cultured meat production by comparing between different bioprocess design scenarios. This was done by carrying out a life cycle assessment (LCA) for a bioprocess system using hollow fiber bioreactors, and utilizing bench-scale experimental data for C2C12 cell proliferation, differentiation and media metabolism. Scenario and sensitivity analyses were used to test the impact of changes in the system design, data sources, and LCA methods on the results to support process design decision making. We compared alternative scenarios to a baseline of C2C12 cells cultured in hollow fiber bioreactors using media consisting of DMEM with serum, for a 16-day proliferation stage and 7-day differentiation stage. The baseline LCA used the average UK electricity mix as the energy source, and heat treatment for wastewater sterilization. The greatest reduction in environmental impacts were achieved with the scenarios using CHO cell metabolism instead of C2C12 cell metabolism (64–67 % reduction); achieving 128 % cell biomass increase during differentiation instead of no increase (42–56 % reduction); using wind electricity instead of average UK electricity (6–39 % reduction); and adjusting the amino acid use based on experimental data (16–27 % reduction). The use of chemical wastewater treatment instead of

Abbreviations: C2C12, muscle cell line; CED, Cumulative Energy Demand; CHO, Chinese Hamster Ovarian; CIP, Clean-in-place; CMB, Cultured Meat Baseline; CMB128, Cultured Meat Baseline with 128% mass increase during differentiation; CMC, Cultured Meat Combined; DMEM, Delbecco's Modified Eagle Medium; FBS, Fetal Bovine Serum; FU, Functional Unit; GWP, Global warming potential; LCA, Life Cycle Assessment; LCIA, Life Cycle Impact Assessment; SIP, Steam-in-place.

* Corresponding author at: Future Sustainable Food Systems Research Group, Department of Agricultural Sciences, Faculty of Agriculture and Forestry, P.O. Box 27, University of Helsinki, 00014 Helsinki, Finland.

E-mail address: hanna.tuomisto@helsinki.fi (H.L. Tuomisto).

<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.158051>

Received 11 November 2021; Received in revised form 18 July 2022; Accepted 11 August 2022

Available online 17 August 2022

0048-9697/© 2022 The Authors. Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

heat treatment increased all environmental impacts, except energy demand, by 1–16 %. This study provides valuable insights for the cultured meat field to understand the effects of different process design scenarios on environmental impacts, and therefore provides a framework for deciding where to focus development efforts for improving the environmental performance of the production system.

1. Introduction

A product of cellular agriculture, cultured meat (i.e. cultivated, clean, cell-based or in vitro meat), is produced by cultivating muscle cells in a bioreactor utilizing tissue engineering technologies and methods (Post et al., 2020). The technology is currently in the development phase for this application. Cultured meat has potential to provide a way to produce meat with lower negative environmental impacts and reduced utilization of animals than conventional livestock production, and provide benefits to human health (Stephens et al., 2018). Currently, agriculture is one of the main contributors to negative environmental impacts (Campbell et al., 2017), and the predicted increase in the consumption of animal-sourced foods has been estimated to contribute to the global food systems exceeding the safe limits for the planetary boundaries by 2050 (Willett et al., 2019).

Previous prospective life cycle assessment (LCA) studies of cultured meat (Tuomisto and Teixeira de Mattos, 2011; Mattick et al., 2015; CE Delft, 2021) indicate that cultured meat production has relatively high energy use, but lower land use when compared to livestock meat and lower global warming potential (GWP) than beef. These studies all show that production of the ingredients for the culture medium of cultured meat and the energy requirement of the bioreactor used for the cultured meat production are the major factors affecting the environmental impacts of cultured meat production. Some studies have adapted the data from the previous LCA studies, and found that the changes in the way of producing culture medium ingredients (Smetana et al., 2015) or use of different climate change assessment methods (Lynch and Pierrehumbert, 2019) can have a major impact on the results of the study. As operational large-scale cultured meat production facilities do not currently exist, all the LCA studies of cultured meat are based on modelling and assumptions (supplemented with confidential data collected from start-up companies in a case of a non-peer reviewed report (CE Delft, 2021)), and therefore, have large uncertainty.

The aim of this paper is to compare process design scenarios to each other to improve the understanding of the sources of, and ways to reduce, the environmental impact of cultured meat (i.e. cultivated muscle cells) production based on a more sophisticated bioprocessing system design than in the previous studies. The main novelties of this cultured meat LCA study are: i) comparison of different design scenarios for a comprehensively-designed bioprocess; ii) the utilization of data for nutrient requirements from laboratory-scale muscle cell line (C2C12) culture proliferation and differentiation experiments, instead of solely relying on modelling and assumptions based on other cell types (e.g. Chinese Hamster Ovary (CHO) cells); and iii) the comparison of a wide range of various system design scenarios to use as a framework to make process design decisions for low environmental impact cultured meat production. The results of this paper are compared with examples of beef and poultry meat production systems to provide further illustration of the areas of development needs. As this paper is targeted at comparison with different bioprocess design scenarios, it does not provide a thorough comparison to the environmental impacts of conventionally produced livestock meat across wide range of different farming systems or a comparison of cultured meat with plant-based foods and other alternative protein sources; for this readers are directed to other papers comparing environmental impacts of different foods (Rubio et al., 2020; Van Eenennaam and Werth, 2021). The findings are intended as a framework to inform research and development towards areas for improving the environmental performance of cultured meat production systems.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. LCA scope, functional unit and system boundaries

LCA was used to estimate the environmental impacts of cultured meat produced in a bioprocess using hollow fiber bioreactors located in Wales in the United Kingdom (UK). A hollow fiber bioreactor was selected for its compact design and benefits this brings in terms of reduced space, stainless-steel use and cleaning and sterilization requirements relative to other configurations per unit of product. Hollow fiber bioreactors have been used to culture cells at $1-2 \times 10^8$ cells/mL of the intra- or extracapillary space depending on the location of the cells (Blute et al., 1988; Chresand et al., 1988; Scragg, 1991; Nankervis et al., 2018), compared to up to 2×10^6 cells/mL for adherent cells on microcarriers in stirred tank bioreactors (Jossen et al., 2018). The comparative holding volume also decreases the amount of media and cleaning consumables required. LCA method (ISO, 2006) was used to assess environmental impacts of a functional unit (FU) of 1 kg (30 % dry matter content and 20 % protein content) of cultured meat consisting of skeletal muscle cells. The LCA was performed by using OpenLCA 1.10.12 software (GreenDelta), and the ReCiPe Midpoint 2016 (H) method (Huijbregts et al., 2017) and Cumulative Energy Demand (CED) (Ecoinvent) for the impact assessment. The environmental impact categories were selected based on the relevance to the product systems, including cumulative energy demand (later energy demand), water consumption, terrestrial acidification, ozone formation, land use, freshwater eutrophication, fossil resource scarcity and fine particulate matter formation (later particulate matter).

The system boundaries covered the main processes from extraction of raw materials up to the factory gate as 'pure' muscle cells, including extraction of raw materials, production of energy, production of inputs for the cultured meat culture medium, energy requirements for bioreactor operations and temperature control and cleaning of the bioreactor (Fig. 1). The build of the facility and equipment (e.g. stainless steel) as well as the downstream processing and packaging of the product were excluded from the analysis. After the filtration process included in the study, the cells can be directly cooked or used as an ingredient in processed foods, and therefore, the product is analogous to fresh uncooked meat and considered as the same endpoint as conventional meat production. Also, the impacts of the production of the bioreactors were not included as the bioreactors can be used for 20 years and the stainless steel can be recycled afterwards resulting in minimal impacts per FU. Additional energy requirements envisioned by the authors, which have not been accounted for in this study as they are secondary considerations to the bioprocess design, include energy for unit operations such as an oxygenator to supply the desired dissolved oxygen concentration, a means of cell dissociation and separation during passaging, and a means of mechanical or electrical stimulation during the differentiation phase. The extraction of the starter cells and the upstream impacts of rearing the donating animal were also excluded. The bioprocess produces lactate and ammonia as co-products that were assumed to be extracted and utilized in other processes. However, in the baseline scenario the environmental impacts of the cultured meat production process were not allocated to the co-products but all impacts were allocated to cultured meat and a cut-off principle was applied to these products (i.e. the impacts that are associated with those products after they leave the factory gate were not considered).

2.2. Baseline system

The bioprocess design for this study is based on current accepted practice for tissue culture of skeletal muscle in a hollow fiber bioreactor system.

Fig. 1. System boundaries and simplified process flow diagram representation of the cultured meat production process.

The system design is explained in detail in the Supplementary Information (SI) and summarized here. The system consists of a series of three different sizes of hollow fiber bioreactors (1×0.23 L, 1×12.6 L and 12×21.3 L) that include polystyrene fibers as scaffolds. The cell culture is passaged between the bioreactors starting from the smallest ending in the largest. The final bioreactors are used for both proliferation and differentiation. The bioprocess consists of 16-day proliferation stage when the cells duplicate, and 7-day differentiation stage when the cells differentiate and fuse together into myotubes and produce proteins. The fibers are assumed to be used for 3 batches and the bioreactor is cleaned between the batches by using sodium hydroxide solution at 77.5 °C and sterilized with saturated steam at 121 °C and 2.1 bar. In the **cultured meat baseline (CMB)** scenario, the culture medium consists of a high glucose Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM) basal media and fetal bovine serum (FBS) supplementation (10 % FBS during proliferation and 2 % FBS during differentiation). The fresh DMEM media components are added in powder form. A preheater is used for heating the media up to 37 °C before it enters the bioreactor. The hollow fiber bioreactor includes a jacket to ensure an isothermal environment is maintained for the cells at a temperature of 37 °C. The jacket is capable of both heating and cooling, as the number of cells within the reactors increases during the proliferation phase and so the heat of reaction released increases with time. The system includes separations units for potentially valuable side products (i.e. lactate and ammonia) and waste products (i.e. cell debris), and therefore, enable water recycling. In order to inactivate residual mammalian cells present in the media prior to drain disposal, the spent culture medium is heat treated by exposure to 80 °C for 1 min.

2.3. Alternative scenarios

The impacts of various alternative bioprocess designs were compared as explained below. The names of the scenarios that are later used in the results section are indicated with **bold italics**.

1. **Energy sources**. In the **CMB** scenario, the average UK electricity mix was assumed to be used for the direct energy use for the cultured meat production process (e.g. bioreactor energy use, cleaning and water sterilization) and the default energy sources for the inputs were used. In the **wind energy** and **solar energy** scenarios the electricity source

for the direct energy use for the cultured meat production process, and the energy source for amino acid production were changed to wind or solar energy, respectively. The energy sources of the other inputs were not changed, and therefore, the wind and solar energy scenarios are not completely independent of fossil fuels.

2. **Culture medium formulations**. In the **CMB** scenario, the culture medium was assumed to consist of DMEM and FBS (SI Table S7–8), which are currently commonly used for mammalian cell cultures, with DMEM requirements calculated as a function of the glucose consumption from our experimental data (SI Sections 3 & 4.5). As the amino acid content of DMEM is not optimized for cultured meat production, a scenario **adjusted amino acids** was included. In that scenario, the amino acid content of DMEM was adjusted according to the actual amino acid intake by the cell culture as determined by laboratory experiments (SI Table S9 & S10). In this scenario, the use of FBS was the same as in the baseline scenario.

As an aim in cultured meat production is to minimize the use of animal-based ingredients, the impacts of using serum-free medium were assessed. In the **serum-free baseline** scenario, the culture medium consisting of only serum-free Essential 8™ medium (Chen et al., 2011) was used in the same quantity as the combined volume of DMEM and FBS used in the baseline scenario. The population doubling time, medium requirements and the cell yield were the same as in the **CMB** scenario. The impact on cell yield was tested in **serum-free experimental** -scenario, where the experimental population doubling time of the cells of 25.9 h was used (instead of 20 h used in the **CMB** scenario) and the specific rate of glucose consumption increased also based on experimental data for C2C12 cells cultured with serum-free Essential 8™ medium.

3. **Experimental population doubling time**. The impact of shortening the doubling time of C2C12 cells from 20 h to 16.6 h based on experimental data was tested in the **doubling time experimental** scenario. The shorter doubling time reduces the medium requirements (SI Section 4.6).

4. **Cell biomass increase during differentiation**. The most conservative estimate used in the baseline model assumed 0 % dry mass increase during the differentiation phase. The highest estimate of **128 % mass**

increase was based on a sensitivity performed in a previous study (Mattick et al., 2015). This mass increase was confirmed experimentally for C2C12 cells in this study based on the total protein increase after a 7 day differentiation period (SI Figs. S5 & S6). The medium level estimate of **63 % mass increase** was selected as the mid-point of those two estimates (SI Section 4.6.3).

- Seawater for cooling the bioreactor.** In the baseline scenario, electricity was assumed to be used for cooling the bioreactor. As this plant is designed for the coastal location in Wales, cool seawater could be used for cooling. In the **seawater cooling** scenario, sea water in average temperature of 12.5 °C (World sea temperature, 2018) was assumed to be used for cooling the bioreactor and replacing the electricity required for cooling. A simple filter and pump would be required to remove debris, however this was not included in the process design.
- Water recycling.** In the baseline scenario, it was assumed that none of the water used in the culture medium was recycled, whereas in the **water recycling** scenario 75 % recycling of that water was assumed based on the recovery of a reverse osmosis (RO) purification unit assumed sufficient as feed media (made up from water for injection grade water produced by RO/electro-deionization) was sterilized via microfiltration prior to introduction into the system (SI Section 5.1).
- Wastewater decontamination.** In the baseline scenario, heat treatment was used for decontamination of wastewater before drain disposal. The **chemical wastewater decontamination** scenario, assessed the impacts of using 10,000 ppm sodium hypochlorite (ECACC, 2010) treatment for the decontamination instead of the heat treatment.
- Cell removal from scaffold.** In the **CMB** scenario, the use of specific substances for removing cells from the scaffold were not included. The use of **TrypLE™** for removing the cells from the scaffold was included as a scenario in the sensitivity analysis.
- Different cell types.** In order to compare the results for C2C12 cells with other cell types, the cultivation of cells with a more efficient metabolism, scenario **CHO cells**, was modelled using literature values for CHO cell specific consumption/production rates of metabolites. CHO cells, having been optimized over decades for the biotechnology industry, have been used to represent the possible properties of a potential future cell line with optimized metabolism, designed for cultured meat production (Mattick et al., 2015).
- Cultured meat – baseline (CMB), cultured meat -baseline with 128 % mass increase (CMB128) and Cultured meat – combined (CMC) scenarios.** To simplify the wide range of potential scenario combinations, the **CMB**, **CMB128** and **CMC** scenarios were created (Table 1): **CMB** describes the **baseline scenario** that does not apply any of the improvement options, whereas **CMB128** is similar to **CMB** but includes 128 % mass increase during the differentiation period. **CMC** consists of a mix of improvement options selected from the categories presented above as shown in Table 1.

2.4. Bioprocess data

Energy use requirements of the system, proliferation and differentiation medium requirements, and cell yields, are based on a combination of

experiments and modelling carried out by the authors. The detailed description is provided in the SI (SI Sections 3–5) and a brief overview is given here. The estimates regarding the data for medium requirements and amino acid use for the proliferation and differentiation of the immortalized murine myoblast cell line C2C12s were based on well-plate experiments. The authors acknowledge the range of primary and immortalized cell options available and under development. The authors anticipate that in the future, cell lines will be designed for the cultured meat field, as has happened in the biotech industry with for example CHO cells, therefore we see the C2C12 cell line as a good intermediary between primary cells and the hypothetical future cell line.

Experiments were conducted because to the authors' knowledge no literature data is available for the metabolic requirements during differentiation of muscle progenitor cells to myotubes. The data for the medium requirements of CHO cells during proliferation was based on data from literature (Buchsteiner et al., 2018) and differentiation assumes a reduction in metabolism to 30 % of proliferation metabolism based on the empirical reduction seen for glucose consumption by C2C12 cells in this study. The oxygen requirements are based on a literature consumption rate for C2C12 cells (Li et al., 2013). The impact of a mass increase during differentiation has been modelled as a reduction in the number of cells required from proliferation to achieve the same final product mass. The media requirements are based on the cell metabolic requirements and are largely independent of the bioreactor design.

The bioprocess includes hollow fiber bioreactors used for both the proliferation and differentiation phase with a theoretical design sized to satisfy passaging at 80 % confluence with a confluence density of 1.1×10^8 cells per mL of extracapillary space. The hollow fibers and scaffold for adherent culture are made of porous polystyrene as developed and used in the author's lab (Luetchford et al., 2018). The different sizes of the bioreactor vessels were used to estimate the reactor energy requirements for heating/cooling to maintain isothermal conditions of 37 °C. The additional energy requirements of the bioprocess that have been accounted for include cleaning and sterilization-in-place (CIP & SIP), media heating, mixing, sterile filtration, and the pumping requirements for media supply and separation units of ultrafiltration, nanofiltration, reverse osmosis and electro-deionization for culture medium component recovery, by-product removal and water purification and recycling.

2.5. LCA data

The detailed description of the life cycle inventory (LCI) and life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) data sources are provided in the Supplementary Data and an overview is shown in Table 2. As a general principle, Ecoinvent 3.6 database (Ecoinvent) was used when possible for inputs such as energy and ingredients of the medium components. The recipes of the DMEM and Essential 8™ were based on ingredients lists from the medium manufacturers. The LCI data for amino acid production and production of other medium ingredients were based on Marinussen and Kool (2010) and Mattick et al. (2015). Regarding quantifying the impacts of FBS, substitution approach based on the logic presented in Bier et al. (2012) was used (explained in detail in SI Section 2). In the absence of LCI data for livestock

Table 1

Characteristics of cultured meat – baseline (**CMB**), cultured meat -baseline with 128 % mass increase during differentiation (**CMB128**) and cultured meat – combined (**CMC**) scenarios.

	CMB	CMB128	CMC
Cell type, differentiation time	C2C12 cells, 7 days differentiation	as CMB	C2C12 cells, 7 days differentiation
Energy source	Average UK electricity mix used for bioreactor energy, cleaning, water sterilization and production amino acids	as CMB	Wind energy used for bioreactor energy, cleaning, water sterilization and production of amino acids
Culture medium	DMEM + FBS, the amount of amino acids not optimized	as CMB	Essential 8™ (no FBS), the amount of amino acids not optimized
Cell biomass increase during differentiation	0 %	128 %	128 %
Use of seawater for cooling of the bioreactor	No	No	Yes
Water recycling	No	No	Yes

Table 2

Life cycle inventory (LCI) data for cultured meat baseline (**CMB**), cultured meat baseline 128 (**CMB128**) and cultured meat combined (**CMC**) scenarios and standard deviations in brackets, for the functional unit of 1 kg of cultured meat.

	Inputs	Unit	CMB	CMB128	CMC	LCI data source
Medium ingredients	DMEM	L	403.1 (77.1)	176.9 (33.8)		1, 2, 3
	FBS (as urea)	kg	0.19 (0.05)	0.08 (0.02)		3
	Serum free medium	L			176.9 (30.3)	1, 2, 3
	Glutamine	kg	0.10 (0.02)	0.04 (0.01)	0.04 (0.01)	1, 3
	Tap water	L	403.1 (77.1)	176.9 (33.8)	52.2 (8.9)	3
Bioprocess	Average UK electricity	MJ	19.2 (2.9)	8.4 (1.3)		3
	Wind electricity	MJ			8.4 (1.3)	3
	Oxygen	kg	0.56 (0.06)	0.24 (0.02)	0.24 (0.02)	3
	Polystyrene	kg	1.10 (0.01)	0.05 (0.005)	0.05 (0.005)	3
Cleaning of the bioreactor	Average UK electricity	MJ	1.71 (0.17)	0.85 (0.09)		3
	Wind electricity	MJ	0		0.85 (0.09)	3
	Sodium hydroxide	kg	0.06 (0.006)	0.03 (0.003)	0.03 (0.003)	3
	tap water	L	17.7 (1.77)	8.2 (0.82)	8.2 (0.82)	3
Wastewater sterilisation	Average UK electricity	MJ	15.5 (1.55)	6.8 (0.68)		3
	Wind electricity	MJ			1.78 (0.18)	3
	Outputs					
	Cultured meat	kg	1	1	1	
	Lactate	kg	1.74	0.77	0.77	
	Ammonia	g	2.2	1.0	1.0	
	Wastewater	L	420.8	187.0	52.2	3

LCI data sources: ¹ Mattick et al. (2015), ² Marinussen and Kool (2010), ³ Ecoinvent.

production in the UK, the data for beef production in Ireland and poultry production in Netherlands based on Agri-footprint database (Agri-footprint 5.0) with economic allocation was used for the comparisons with livestock meat. These systems were selected for the comparison due to the suitability of the data with the impact assessment methods used in this study and the availability of data from locations that are the closest to the UK.

2.6. Uncertainty and sensitivity analyses

Monte Carlo analysis was used for estimating the uncertainty regarding the data used for the **CMB**, **CMB128** and **CMC** scenarios. The uncertainty ranges used in the Monte Carlo analysis (Supplementary Data) were based on the standard deviations of the bioreactor energy use and medium requirement estimates, whereas for the polystyrene requirements, the impacts of cleaning operations, the amount of wastewater generated and oxygen inputs, the uncertainty ranges were set to $\pm 10\%$ as more detailed data was not available. The Monte Carlo analysis was carried out in Excel using 1200 replications based on uniform distribution for the random number generation of the variables within the uncertainty ranges.

A sensitivity analysis was used for examining the impact of changes in single input values to the results. In addition, the sensitivity of the allocation method choices was tested. The impacts of allocating impacts to lactate as a co-product of the cultured meat production system were assessed by using two alternative methods: i) mass allocation and ii) product substitution (details in SI Section 2). Regarding the impacts of FBS, in addition to product substitution that was used in the baseline scenario, a combination of economic and dry mass-based allocation was used (details in SI Section 2).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Comparison of culture medium scenarios

When considering the scenarios for culture media alone, the highest contribution to most of the environmental impacts of the culture medium was the production of amino acids, followed by glucose, and vitamins and minerals both in the case of the standard medium containing DMEM and FBS (Fig. 2A) and the serum-free medium (Fig. 2B). The contribution of FBS was 0.2–13 % of the total impact of the standard culture medium, depending on the impact category, when substitution-based allocation was used. The production of the growth factors contributed 0.5–1.7 % to the impacts of serum-free medium.

Fig. 2. Contribution of different ingredients to the environmental impacts of the culture medium used in CMB and CMB128 consisting of DMEM and FBS (Fetal Bovine Serum) and serum-free medium (Essential 8™) used in CMC.

Fig. 3. Comparison of the environmental impacts of different culture medium alternatives to the CMB medium consisting of DMEM and fetal bovine serum (FBS).

The serum-free medium (Essential 8™) had 28–44 % lower environmental impacts compared to the culture medium used in the CMB (Fig. 3), when directly substituted for the baseline medium and assuming no reduction in cell yield or change in cell metabolism. Of note is that the need for supplementation of additional growth factors beyond those included in Essential 8 (insulin, FGF2 and TGFβ1) has not been accounted for in the serum-free medium scenario. The lowest impacts were achieved by using wind energy for the production of amino acids combined with adjustment of the amino acid supply according to the requirements of the cells instead of using the standard DMEM formulation, indicating the importance of using a cell line with relatively low amino acid requirements.

3.2. Comparison of cultured meat scenarios

The environmental impacts of the CMB were 1.7–2.3 times higher compared to the CMB128 and 3.8–5.7 times higher compared to the impacts of the CMC depending on the impact category (Table 3).

The production of the culture medium had the highest contribution to all impact categories both in the case of CMB and CMC (Fig. 4). Bioprocess energy use and wastewater treatment were the second most contributing processes for CMB, whereas in the case of CMC the second most contributing process varied between the impact categories (Fig. 4).

When comparing the range of scenarios to the CMB, the highest reductions in all the environmental impacts were achieved through changing the cell type to CHO cells, and assuming 128 % mass increase during differentiation phase of C2C12 cells (Fig. 5). These reductions were mainly due to the decrease in culture medium requirements from 426 L in the CMB, to

187 L when assuming 128 % mass increase for the C2C12 cells during the differentiation period, and to 138 L/kg of cultured meat when CHO cells were assumed to be used. The 128 % mass increase reduces medium requirements as less cells from the proliferation phase are needed per FU when compared to the 0 % mass increase scenario. Relatively high reductions compared to the other processes were also achieved through use of wind or solar energy instead of 'average electricity mix' in the bioprocess and production of medium ingredients; with the adjustment of amino acid inputs according to the experimentally deduced requirements of the C2C12 cells (Fig. 5). As noted above, the use of serum-free medium reduced the environmental impacts when a direct substitute with the baseline media recipe was considered (serum-free baseline), Fig. 5). The impacts of serum-free experimental were increased by 1–19 % to that of CMB as a consequence of the higher cell doubling time of 25.9 h observed in laboratory experiments, compared to the 20 h baseline value. The doubling time experimental scenario, with a cell population doubling time of 16.6 h, reduced the environmental impacts by approximately 8–9 % compared to CMB. The use of seawater as cooling water for the bioreactors reduced the energy use for cooling, but this had only minor effect on the results (Fig. 5), of less than 1 % impact reduction. Water recycling reduced the environmental impacts due to reduction in the volume of water needed to be sterilized before disposal and to be treated at the wastewater treatment plant (Fig. 5). Using chemical decontamination instead of heat inactivation for the used culture medium before drain disposal substantially increased all impact categories except energy demand (Fig. 5). The use of TrypLE™ for removing the cells from scaffold had only minor impacts on the results (Fig. 5).

Table 3

Environmental impacts of cultured meat baseline (CMB), cultured meat baseline 128 (CMB128) and cultured meat combined (CMC) scenarios (mean and standard deviations (SD) based on Monte Carlo analysis).

Impact category	Unit	CMB		CMB128		CMC	
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Particulate matter	kg PM2.5 eq	0.039	0.008	0.019	0.008	0.010	0.002
Fossil resource scarcity	kg oil eq	7.60	1.33	3.83	1.32	1.33	0.21
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Global warming	kg CO2 eq	25.19	4.60	12.64	4.55	4.88	0.81
Land use	m2a crop eq	6.89	1.33	3.36	1.27	1.84	0.33
Ozone formation	kg NOx eq	0.052	0.011	0.026	0.011	0.012	0.002
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO2 eq	0.12	0.02	0.06	0.02	0.03	0.01
Water consumption	m3	0.54	0.43	0.32	0.32	0.12	0.02
Cumulative energy demand	MJ-eq	532.78	326.08	231.43	177.36	94.09	15.62

Fig. 4. Contribution of different processes on the environmental impacts of cultured meat baseline (CMB) scenario and cultured meat combined (CMC) scenario.

3.3. Comparison of cultured meat with livestock meat

The comparison of the impacts of CMB, CMB128 and CMC with conventionally produced beef and poultry shows that the relative differences vary highly between the impact categories (Fig. 6). CMB had the highest impact in five out of nine environmental impact categories, whereas beef had the highest impact in the rest of the impact categories. Poultry had the lowest impacts in all of the impact categories. CMC had lower impact than beef in all impact categories, except freshwater eutrophication. CMB128 had lower impacts than beef in all impact categories, except

particulate matter, fossil resource scarcity, freshwater eutrophication and energy demand. The relatively high freshwater eutrophication impacts in CMB, CMB128 and CMC scenarios were explained by phosphorus emissions from non-agricultural sources, such as wastewater treatment processes related to production of energy and materials used for the production of inputs.

3.4. Sensitivity analysis outputs of data and methods

When considering only the uncertainties related to the bioprocess design, the sensitivity analysis showed that the CMB system was the most sensitive to the uncertainties regarding medium quantities, the difference ranging between ± 10 and 18 % depending on the impact category (Fig. 7).

However, the choices in the allocation methods had even higher impact on the results. In this study, lactate is taken as a waste product, though it should be noted that in theory, it may be economically feasible for waste valorization, that is to say lactate could be considered as a co-product not a waste product thus changing the LCA and resulting environmental impacts. The use of dry mass-based allocation for lactate and cultured meat (i.e. the environmental impacts of the whole production process were allocated to cultured meat and lactate based on their dry matter mass) reduced the impacts of cultured meat by 85 % in the CMB scenario compared to the baseline where all impacts were allocated to cultured meat (Table 4). Dry mass-based allocation used for FBS (i.e. the environmental impacts of beef production were allocated to FBS as a basis of its dry matter weight in relation to the dry matter mass of the rest of products from beef systems) increased the impacts of CMB by 11–3041 % depending on the impact category (Table 4).

3.5. Comparison of the results with previous LCA studies

Direct comparisons of the results from different LCA studies are not usually possible due to variation in the system boundaries, allocation methods and background data sources, and therefore, the comparisons need to be done carefully and with this in mind. The GWP of CMB was close to the findings of Smetana et al. (2015) and within the upper end of the uncertainty range in Mattick et al. (2015) (Table 5). The land use requirements of CMB were also close to the upper end of the uncertainty found in Mattick et al. (2015), whereas the land use in Smetana et al. (2015) was substantially lower due to the assumption of using cyanobacteria as a main source of nutrients. CMC had higher GWP than the renewable energy scenario in the report by CE Delft (2021). This could be explained by the

Fig. 5. Comparison of the environmental impacts of different scenarios as percentage change compared to the CMB scenario.

Fig. 6. Comparison of the relative impacts of cultured meat baseline (CMB), cultured meat baseline with 128 % cell mass increase during differentiation (CMB128) and cultured meat combined (CMC) scenarios with beef produced in Ireland and poultry in the Netherlands.

fact that the direct electricity use for the bioreactors had the highest contribution to the GWP in the report by CE Delft (2021), whereas in this study the production of medium had the highest contribution to the GWP. Even though wind energy was assumed to be used in the CMC scenario for direct energy use at the production plant and for the production of amino acids, relative high amount of fossil-based energy was still needed for the production of other ingredients for the medium. The estimates by Tuomisto and Teixeira de Mattos (2011) had the lowest impacts in all categories due to the fact that the system design was based on a futuristic design using cyanobacteria-based culture medium. The differences between the results of this study and Mattick et al. (2015) are explained by the differences in

the system design, for instance, Mattick et al. (2015) assumed the use of stirred-tank bioreactor and serum-free media with soya hydrolysate as a replacement of FBS. Furthermore, Mattick et al. (2015) assumed the production to take place in the US, no cell passaging was reportedly accounted for and a shorter differentiation period of 3 days compared to 7 days in this study (SI Table S1).

As the study by Smetana et al. (2015) did not provide enough detail for a comparison to be made to explain the differences between their findings and other studies, additional information was gained by personal communication with the lead author. Even though Smetana et al. (2015) used data from Tuomisto and Teixeira de Mattos (2011), their results for the environmental impacts were substantially higher due to the assumption that the cyanobacteria for the culture medium was cultivated in a bioreactor rather than in an open pond leading to substantially higher energy consumption.

3.6. Identifying hotspots and where to focus research and development efforts

This paper utilizes biochemical engineering design methodologies and laboratory experiments. However, aside from the cell culture data and other data taken from experimental research papers, this bioprocess design

Fig. 7. Results of the sensitivity analysis related to the uncertainties of the process design when single parameters are reduced by standard deviation (as shown in Table 2).

Table 4

Impact of lactate and FBS allocation choices to the environmental impacts compared to the baseline scenario (CMB). For CMB all impacts of the process were allocated to cultured meat, lactate was regarded as by-product without any allocation, and substitution-based allocation was used for FBS. Here we consider substitution, dry mass and wet mass-based allocation for lactate and dry mass based allocation for FBS (as explained in SI Section 2).

	Lactate allocation			FBS allocation
	Substitution	Dry mass allocation	Wet mass allocation	Dry mass
	%	%	%	%
Land use	-5	-85	-63	3041
Global warming	-35	-85	-63	252
Fossil resource scarcity	-48	-85	-63	11
Freshwater eutrophication	-29	-85	-63	85
Particulate matter	-23	-85	-63	129
Ozone formation	-35	-85	-63	97
Terrestrial acidification	-20	-85	-63	241
Water consumption	-28	-85	-63	348
Energy demand	-32	-85	-63	28

Table 5

Comparison of the results for Global Warming Potential (GWP) and land use of the cultured meat baseline (CMB) and cultured meat combined (CMC) scenarios in this study with findings of the previous studies.

	GWP (kg CO ₂ -eq/kg product)	Land use (m ² /kg product)
This study	CMC 4.9, CMB128 12.6 CMB 25.2	CMC 1.8, CMB128 3.4, CMB 6.9
CE Delft (2021)	2.5–13.5	1.7–1.8
Mattick et al. (2015)	3.0–25.5	1.5–9.5
Smetana et al. (2015)	23.9–24.6	0.4–0.8
Tuomisto and Teixeira de Mattos (2011)	1.9–2.2	0.2

is still theoretical, and as such several assumptions have been made, as described through this manuscript. This study does not aim to present a final, fully-detailed bioprocess design but rather identify the impact on the overall media requirements and environmental impact for an illustrative set of bioprocess design scenarios that previous simplified designs have not considered.

The results of this paper align with findings of previous LCA studies by indicating that cultured meat could have potential to reduce the environmental impacts of food production, especially when replacing beef and appropriate design decisions are made. Though, the authors recognize that wide-ranging and continually-improving conventional farming methods mean there is considerable variation in environmental impacts, analysis of which is beyond the scope of this bioprocess-focused study. The results here show that the major hotspot of the environmental impacts of cultured meat is the production of the culture medium ingredients, in particular synthetic amino acids. Further research is needed to find alternative sources for amino acids, for instance using hydrolysates from legumes, algae or microbes. The areas to focus research and development (R&D) efforts are biological and bioprocess design choices that are discussed here.

In terms of biological areas for development, there is currently limited literature data available specific to skeletal muscle cell culture including C2C12 cells. Cell mass, cell water content, cell protein content, heat of reaction of cell growth and cell maintenance are based on literature values. To account for the lack of information available on how cell metabolism changes for skeletal muscle cells during differentiation, experiments with C2C12 cells were conducted with the notable outcome that on a per nuclei basis they consume less medium components when differentiating compared to proliferating. The ratio of this decrease and metabolism change is an important biological area to be explored for muscle cells from different species. The mass increase during differentiation was identified as a key area of uncertainty early on in this study, with a large effect on the environmental impacts, consequently experiments were undertaken in this study to reduce this uncertainty. We determined the total protein increase of C2C12 cells during differentiation (SI Section 4.6.3). A linear relationship was observed for protein increase against differentiation time (SI Fig. S6), up to day 9 of differentiation. This highlights the length of the differentiation phase as an area for optimization. Longer cell culturing time may be required for achieving whole-cut cultured meat with more complex media requirements if co-cultures are also used. Further R&D should also investigate the extent of confluency required combined with the length of differentiation phase needed for achieving a desired protein yield.

3.7. Medium formulation and the use of serum

The authors anticipate the elimination of animal derived products from cultured meat production; however, they acknowledge the current widespread use of serum. In this study FBS was taken as the baseline scenario because it is still widely used in cell culture, due to the associated high-costs and reported efficiency-disparity of serum-free alternatives. Alongside the questionable ethics of serum use, it is associated with disadvantages of batch-to-batch variation, limited availability, and the underlying requirement for using animals. Therefore, this study further evaluated the environmental impacts of a chemically-defined, serum-free media alternative

(Essential 8™) that is currently commercially available. The use of Essential 8™ is in our experience a potential alternative, noting that it is currently up to 10 times the price of DMEM and FBS, and results in significantly lower proliferation rates for C2C12s demonstrates that there is still development work required on serum alternatives. Various research groups and companies are currently developing new formulations of serum-free medium and animal-free growth factors, by using different ingredients that may have vastly different levels of environmental impacts compared to this study (Stout et al., 2021). There is potential that alternative amino acid sources could help to reduce the impacts, with R&D needed here. R&D will also be required to determine the quantity of different ingredients needed for both the proliferation and differentiation phases, as well as their stability in the chosen bioreactor system.

3.8. Whole-cut versus protein ingredient

This study produces a cell slurry, an ingredient to add to a recipe to make the desired product. There is growing interest in whole-cut cultured meat, which introduces other design challenges at all stages of bioprocess design out of scope of this study. For example, some may wish to include co-culture with adipocytes, plus consideration for how texture and structure is achieved.

3.9. Bioreactor optimization

Preliminary bioreactor design related to the minimum and maximum cell densities is based on literature for hollow-fiber bioreactors, but are not specific to muscle cells alone. Bioreactor size is based on a theoretical design achieved using chemical engineering design methodologies, and while it has not been built, it is within the size limits of membrane units manufactured for other industries. The physical limits associated with cell culture to satisfy oxygen requirements have yet to be determined empirically. Further work is required to optimize design for maximum cell (protein) yield, and minimum operating and capital expenditures, as well as minimal environmental impact and maximum ethical standards.

3.10. Bioprocess design

Due to the energy requirements for cultured meat production, the use of renewable energy sources is key for achieving the climate benefits. This choice of energy source is particularly important when considering the longer time frame impacts; the emissions of fossil CO₂ are more problematic than methane emissions as CO₂ persists in the atmosphere indefinitely whereas methane dissipates in 12 years (Lynch and Pierrehumbert, 2019).

The bioreactor design here is based on chemical engineering bioprocess design methodologies. An area of R&D focus is the detailed bioreactor design in conjunction with empirical verification is required to take into account practical size limitations, mass transfer limitations for example associated with oxygen supply, inoculation and passaging methods and seeding efficiency. In addition, the separation units and their respective efficiency and retention specific to the components and formulation of mammalian cell culture medium is uncertain.

3.11. Full effects of livestock reduction

Further consequential LCA studies should also consider other wider consequences of reducing livestock production. For instance, livestock produces many co-products that would need to be replaced with other technologies if cultured meat were to replace livestock production in large quantities. Also, due to the key role of extensive grazing-based livestock production systems in the provision of biodiversity benefits and other ecosystem services (Tälle et al., 2016; Filazzola et al., 2020), more holistic environmental assessments of different food production systems would be needed.

3.12. Consumer studies and socio-economic analysis

The system design presented in this paper would produce a basic cultured meat as a muscle cell mass that could be used as an ingredient in processed meat products. While some studies have investigated the consumers' perceptions of cultured meat (Bryant and Barnett, 2018; Stephens et al., 2018), further studies are needed for organoleptic testing and consumer tasting experiments. Furthermore, to develop the best cultured meat bioprocess for the planet, people and profit, future analysis is recommended in the socio-economic aspects of cultured meat, in addition to the LCA.

4. Conclusion

This study provides a framework to compare between difference bioprocess design scenarios based on environmental impacts. The cultured meat combined (**CMC**) scenario, that consisted of currently available improved technologies, had 73–82 % lower impacts than the cultured meat baseline (**CMB**) scenario. The production of the culture medium ingredients had the highest contribution to the environmental impacts, varying between 48 and 89 % depending on the impact category. The use of CHO cell metabolism, instead of C2C12 cells reduced the environmental impacts by 64–67 %, whereas the use of chemical wastewater treatment instead of heat treatment increased the impacts 0–16 %. When including dry mass-based allocation to the lactate by-product, the impacts of **CMB** were reduced by 85 % compared to the baseline where no allocation was included. **CMB** scenario had higher environmental impacts than poultry in all impact categories and higher impacts than beef in 5 out of 9 impact categories. **CMC** scenario had lower impacts than beef in all impact categories, except freshwater eutrophication, but higher or similar impacts with poultry. This knowledge contributes to improving the understanding of the sources of, and ways to reduce, the environmental impact of cultured meat by using a comprehensively-designed bioprocess that utilizes hollow fiber bioreactors, and the utilization of data for nutrient requirements from laboratory-scale C2C12 culture proliferation and differentiation experiments. Based on the LCA outputs, the authors are able to recommend that the following five areas should be the focus of R&D for improving the environmental performance of cultured meat production systems: i) cell line development to improve culture medium use efficiency and protein yield, ii) culture medium recipe development, iii) use of renewable energy in the bioprocess and production of culture medium ingredients, iv) bioreactor design to reduce energy use, and v) efficient downstream process design to utilize by-products of the bioprocess. We have chosen a range of scenarios that are feasible to illustrate this framework, and encourage others wishing to manufacture cultured meat to utilize this method of analysis of design scenarios as a basis for their own bioprocess design scenarios, incorporating their own data and design choices.

Data availability statement

All data generated or analysed during this study are included in this published article (and its supplementary information files).

Author contributions

H.L.T. and M.J.E conceived the idea. All authors were involved in designing and conducting the study, and writing the paper. S.J.A. conducted the laboratory experiments, data analysis and mathematical modelling related to the system design, guided by M.J.E. The LCA was designed and performed by H.L.T.

Data availability

All data is reported in the article and supplementary information files.

Declaration of competing interest

Hanna Tuomisto and Scott Allan have no conflicts to declare. Marianne Ellis is co-founder of Cellular Agriculture Ltd.

Acknowledgements

Funding

The work carried out at the University of Bath was supported by New Harvest, a 501(c)(3) non-profit research institute (grant #007) and the EPSRC Centre for Doctoral Training in Sustainable Chemical Technologies (EP/L016354/1).

The authors would like to thank the University of Bath for supporting this work and gratefully acknowledge the assistance of Dr. Shaun Reeksting at the University of Bath Material and Chemical Characterisation Facility (MC2) for amino acid detection and analysis via LC-MS. *We also thank the 40+ project students for many enjoyable and thought-provoking discussions on bioprocess design over the years, and Jonathan Torralba Torrón for assisting with the experimental work, conducting proliferation experiments with Essential 8™.*

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.158051>.

References

- Agri-footprint 5.0 (n.d.). LCI Database. Blonk Sustainability, Netherlands.
- Bier, J.M., Verbeek, C.J., Lay, M.C., 2012. An eco-profile of thermoplastic protein derived from blood meal part 1: allocation issues. *Int. J. Life Cycl. Assess.* 17, 208–219.
- Blute, T., Gillies, R.J., Dale, B.E., 1988. Cell density measurements in hollow fiber bioreactors. *Biotechnol. Prog.* 4, 202–209.
- Bryant, C., Barnett, J., 2018. Consumer acceptance of cultured meat: a systematic review. *Meat Sci.* 143, 8–17.
- Buchsteiner, M., Quek, L.E., Gray, P., Nielsen, L.K.J.B., 2018. Improving culture performance and antibody production in CHO cell culture processes by reducing the Warburg effect. *Bioengineering* 115, 2315–2327.
- Campbell, B.M., Beare, D.J., Bennett, E.M., Hall-Spencer, J.M., Ingram, J.S.I., Jaramillo, F., Ortiz, R., Ramankutty, N., Sayer, J.A., Shindell, D., 2017. Agriculture production as a major driver of the earth system exceeding planetary boundaries. *Ecol. Soc.* 22 (4), 8.
- CE Delft, 2021. LCA of Cultivated Meat-Future Projections for Different Scenarios. CE Delft, Delft, p. 50.
- Chen, G., Gulbranson, D.R., Hou, Z., Bolin, J.M., Ruotti, V., Probasco, M.D., Smuga-Otto, K., Howden, S.E., Diol, N.R., Propson, N.E.J.N.m, 2011. Chemically Defined Conditions for Human iPSC Derivation and Culture. 8, pp. 424–429.
- Chresand, T.J., Gillies, R.J., Dale, B.E., 1988. Optimum fiber spacing in a hollow fiber bioreactor. *Biotechnol. Bioeng.* 32, 983–992.
- ECACC, 2010. Fundamental Techniques in Cell Culture - Laboratory Handbook. European Collection of Authenticated Cell Cultures. 4th edition. Public Health England and Sigma-Aldrich. <https://www.culturecollections.org.uk/media/161749/ecacc-lab-handbook-fourth-edition.pdf>.
- Ecoinvent (n.d.). LCI database. Ecoinvent version 3.6. Zurich, Switzerland.
- Filazzola, A., Brown, C., Dettlaff, M.A., Batbaatar, A., Grenke, J., Bao, T., Peetoom Heida, I., Cahill Jr., J.F.J.E.L., 2020. The effects of livestock grazing on biodiversity are multi-trophic: a meta-analysis. *Ecology Letters.* 23 (8), 1298–1309.
- GreenDelta (n.d.). OpenLCA software. Berlin, Germany.
- Huijbregts, M.A.J., Steinmann, Z.J.N., Elshout, P.M.F., Stam, G., Verones, F., Vieira, M., Zijp, M., Hollander, A., van Zelm, R., 2017. ReCiPe2016: a harmonised life cycle impact assessment method at midpoint and endpoint level. *Int. J. Life Cycl. Assess.* 22, 138–147.
- ISO, 2006. ISO14044; Environmental Management - Life Cycle Assessment - Requirements and Guidelines. International Organization for Standardization, Geneva.
- Jossen, V., van den Bos, C., Eibl, R., Eibl, D., 2018. Manufacturing human mesenchymal stem cells at clinical scale: process and regulatory challenges. *Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* 102, 3981–3994.
- Li, W., Hu, Z.-F., Chen, B., Ni, G.-X., 2013. Response of C2C12 myoblasts to hypoxia: the relative roles of glucose and oxygen in adaptive cellular metabolism. *Biomed. Res. Int.* 2013, 326346.
- Luetchford, K.A., Wung, N., Argyle, I.S., Storm, M.P., Weston, S.D., Tosh, D., Ellis, M.J., 2018. Next generation in vitro liver model design: combining a permeable polystyrene membrane with a transdifferentiated cell line. *J. Membr. Sci.* 565, 425–438.
- Lynch, J., Pierrehumbert, R., 2019. Climate impacts of cultured meat and beef cattle. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems* <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2019.00005> 19 February 2019.
- Marinussen, M., Kool, A., 2010. Environmental Impacts of Synthetic Amino Acid Production. Blonk Milieua Advies BV, Gouda, Netherlands.

- Mattick, C.S., Landis, A.E., Allenby, B.R., Genovese, N.J., 2015. Anticipatory life cycle analysis of in vitro biomass cultivation for cultured meat production in the United States. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 49, 11941–11949.
- Nankervis, B., Jones, M., Vang, B., Brent Rice Jr., R., Coeshott Jr., C., Beltzer Jr., J., 2018. Optimizing T cell expansion in a hollow-fiber bioreactor. *Curr Stem Cell Rep* 4, 46–51.
- Post, M.J., Levenberg, S., Kaplan, D.L., Genovese, N., Fu, J., Bryant, C.J., Negowetti, N., Verzijden, K., Moutsatsou, P., 2020. Scientific, sustainability and regulatory challenges of cultured meat. *Nature Food* 1, 403–415.
- Rubio, N.R., Xiang, N., Kaplan, D.L., 2020. Plant-based and cell-based approaches to meat production. *Nat. Commun.* 11, 6276.
- Scragg, A., 1991. *Bioreactors in biotechnology: A practical approach*. Ellis Horwood Ltd., Chichester.
- Smetana, S., Mathys, A., Knoch, A., Heinz, V., 2015. Meat alternatives: life cycle assessment of most known meat substitutes. *Int. J. Life Cycle Assess.* 20, 1254–1267.
- Stephens, N., Di Silvio, L., Dunsford, I., Ellis, M., Glencross, A., Sexton, A., 2018. Bringing cultured meat to market: technical, socio-political, and regulatory challenges in cellular agriculture. *Trends Food Sci. Technol.* 78, 155–166.
- Stout, A.J., Mirliani, A.B., White, E.C., Yuen, J.S., Kaplan, D.L., 2021. Simple and effective serum-free medium for sustained expansion of bovine satellite cells for cell cultured meat. *Nat. Commun. Biol.* 5, 466.
- Tälle, M., Deák, B., Poschlod, P., Valkó, O., Westerberg, L., Milberg, P., 2016. Grazing vs. mowing: a meta-analysis of biodiversity benefits for grassland management. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* 222, 200–212.
- Tuomisto, H.L., Teixeira de Mattos, M.J., 2011. Environmental impacts of cultured meat production. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 45, 6117–6123.
- Van Eenennaam, A., Werth, S., 2021. Animal board invited review: animal agriculture and alternative meats—learning from past science communication failures. *Animal* 15, 100360.
- Willett, W., Rockström, J., Loken, B., Springmann, M., Lang, T., Vermeulen, S., Garnett, T., Tilman, D., DeClerck, F., Wood, A.J.T.L., 2019. Food in the Anthropocene: The EAT–Lancet Commission on Healthy Diets From Sustainable Food Systems. 393, pp. 447–492.
- World sea temperature, 2018. Llanelli Water Temperature. United Kingdom Sea Temperatures.